

Analysis of Aphorisms in Uzbek and English Languages

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Abstract. The purpose of the article is to study the analysis of aphorisms in English and Uzbek. The types of aphorisms in Uzbek and English and their meanings are carefully analyzed, and examples are given that show the peculiarities of aphorisms in the two related languages.

Keywords: Uzbek aphorisms, English aphorisms paremiology, aphorism genre, proverbs, sayings and literature.

1 Introduction

Aphorisms are present in all the nations of the world, and there are different opinions in world paremiology. The question of the artistic form of aphorisms are the only one dominant thought, there is no single concept.

An aphorism (from Greek *aphorismos*, denoting 'delimitation', 'distinction', and 'definition') is a concise, terse, laconic, or memorable expression of a general truth or principle.⁷⁸ They are often handed down by tradition from generation to generation. The concept is generally distinct from those of an adage, brocard, chiasmus, epigram, maxim (legal or philosophical), principle, proverb, and saying; although some of these concepts may be construed as types of aphorism.

It is often based on philosophical, moral and literary principles. To qualify as an aphorism, it is necessary for a statement to contain a truth revealed in a terse manner. Aphoristic statements are quoted in writings as well as in our daily speech. The fact that they contain a truth gives them a universal acceptance. On the contrary to proverbs the origin of wise words belong to an exact person (writer, poet, publicist, philosopher, scientist, statesman and etc.) and retain its individuality.

There is not given any opinion as a rule about aphorisms in literary or annotated dictionaries. The original lexical meaning of the aphorism is supreme wisdom, intelligence. The second meaning is a hidden meaning, a hidden reason, which is difficult to understand. The genre of aphorisms exists in all peoples of the world, and there are different opinions about it in the science of paremiology. According to Luke de Klappe Vovenarg, "If a wise word needs an explanation, then it has not reached the root of the word." Aphorisms have the characteristics of aphorism (adaptation to the expression of wise thought) and sentimentality (exhortation). One of the peculiarities of aphorisms is that in most of them there is a lot of ambiguity, sharp irony, subtlety.

Regarding the artistic nature of aphorisms, it should be noted that the symbols in them are common and apply to everyone. The brevity, expressiveness, clarity and conciseness of the thought also ensure the artistry of the aphorism. Aphorism in the broadest sense is a genre that serves to reveal the qualities of man, his activities and the essence of life. Therefore, it is not enough for any creator to have a sharp mind, to master the secrets of the art of speech to create an aphorism. In order to create an aphorism, the creator must have the above two qualities, as well as his own life experience, his own independent view and conclusion about everything and the event. That is why almost all artists who wrote in the genre of aphorisms turned to this genre only in the last period of their lives. In the course of the study, it became clear that the aphorisms in the Uzbek language. For example:

⁷⁸ [Definition of Aphorism](#) from the [Online Etymology Dictionary](#)

Kimki, yolg‘ on so‘zni birovga to‘nkagay, o‘z qora yuzini yog‘ ga bulaydi. Ozgina yolg‘ on ham ulug‘ gunohdir; ozgina zahar ham halok qiluvchidir. (A. Navoiy)

Adabiyot — hasratdan boshqa narsa emas. Faqat yozuvchining oddiy odamdan farqi – oddiy odam o‘z dardidan hasrat qilsa, yozuvchi birovlar dardidan hasrat qiladi. (Shukur Xolmirzayev)

Mol-dunyoing seni aldamasin, chunki asragan mol-dunyoing boshqalarniki bo‘ladi. Ularni sarf eta olsang, o‘sha seniki bo‘ladi. (Abu Ali Ibn Sino)

Aphorisms often come with a pinch of humor, which makes them more appealing to the masses. Proverbs, maxims, adages and clichés are different forms of aphoristic statements that gain prevalence from generation to generation and frequently appear in our daily speech. Writers often create general issues in their texts in order to convey a moral or philosophical idea they hold to be universally true. The aphorisms are similar to the proverbs. They are both short, memorable wise sayings, but the aphorism belongs to the same person if the proverb belongs to the people or the nation. Some aphorisms become ingrained in the form and become proverbs when they go into public use. Here are some proverbs:

- It’s better to be safe than sorry
- Better late than never
- You catch more flies with honey than with vinegar
- Don’t judge a book by its cover.

Moreover, examples of aphorisms:

This better to have loved and lost/ than never to have loved at all. (Alfred Lloyd Tennyson)

Your children need your presence more than your presents. (Jesse Jackson)

We are what we pretend to be, so we must be careful what we pretend to be. (Kurt Vonnegut)

Need is better than stupidity. (Thomas Gobbs)

2 Methods

The aphorisms in English and Uzbek are identical. Aphorisms are similar in meaning and structure in both languages. There are also categories of aphorisms. According to the meaning of aphorism is divided into many types. They are about health, knowledge, wisdom, etiquette, life, love, happiness and etc.

Famous English writers and playwrights, often used aphorisms in their works, and coined many of them.

English and Uzbek aphorisms are widely found in literature. Many aphorisms used in literature break through their literary use and become relevant in their own sense, apart from the original work in which they appeared.

Mark Twain had a lot to say about life itself, as well as many other related topics. He was quite prolific in his day, so his books and other writings are a treasure trove of interesting sayings. If you're looking for some quotes about life that eloquently tell it like it is, this famous author's words might be exactly what you seek. Human life is maliciously planned with one principal object in view: to make you do all the different kind of things you particularly do not want to do.

Explore a selection of some of the best Mark Twain quotes about life.

Life: we laugh and laugh, then cry and cry, then feebler laugh, then die.

There is no sadder thing than a young pessimist than perhaps an old optimist.

What is human life? The first third a good time; the rest remembering about it.

When we remember we are all mad, the mysteries of life disappear and life stands explained.

3 Conclusion

To conclude, the study of the above aphorisms allows young people to receive advice, guidance or counsel, life conclusions. In general, every word of wisdom is an expression of the wisdom of the people, a generalization of many years of life experience. The appearance of words of wisdom in the language is determined by the history of the people who created them. Many aphorisms were created in ancient times and still live with the people who are their creators. Aphorisms are popular, passed down from generation to generation and live for centuries. As each nation has its own way of thinking, it also affects their wisdom. Even though the themes in the aphorisms are similar, the images in them are unique. The Uzbek people are justifiably proud of their contribution to the world's spiritual treasury. Wisdom is a priceless gift from wise ancestors to future generations.

Aphorisms are a spiritual treasure that is passed down from generation to generation.

References

1. Webster's Revised Unabridged Dictionary. Merriam. 1913.
2. Daintith, J., Stibbs, A., Wright, E. and Pickering, D. (Eds). Bloomsbury Dictionary of Quotations, London: Ted Smart. 1991.
3. Mother tongue. 10th grade. Tashkent. 2017.
4. Annotated dictionary of the Uzbek language. 2 volumes. Volume 2 Moscow, Russkiy Yazik Publishing House. 1981. Uzbek folk tales. The magic word. Navruz. Tashkent. 2017.
5. Fozil Yuldosh ogli. The Epic of Alpomish. Ghafur Ghulam. Tashkent. 2016.
6. A. Navoi. Mahbub ul- qulub. Sano standard. Tashkent. 2018.
7. Ashirbaeva, A. (2020). POSITIVE TRAITS OF TEACHING LANGUAGE THROUGH LITERATURE. *Science and Education*, 1 (Special Issue 2).
8. O'zME. The first volume. Tashkent. 2000.
9. Tashpulatova, D., & Siddiqova, I. (2021, April). A CRITIQUE OF THE VIEW OF ANTONYMY AS A RELATION BETWEEN WORD FORMS. In *Конференции*.
10. Ташпулатова, Д. Х. (2019). ПОНЯТИЕ И ВИДЫ ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКИХ КОНЦЕПЦИЙ ОБУЧЕНИЯ ИНОСТРАННОМУ ЯЗЫКУ. АНАЛИЗ СОВРЕМЕННЫХ ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКИХ КОНЦЕПЦИЙ. *Вопросы педагогики*, (7-2), 118-121.
11. ТАШПУЛАТОВА, Д. PRAGMATIC APHORISMS IN UZBEK AND ENGLISH FEATURE AND THE PRINCIPLES OF THEIR TRANSMISSION IN THE CORPUS. *СООТНОШЕНИЕ ПАРАЛИНГВИСТИКИ И РЕЧЕВОГО ЭТИКЕТА В РАЗНЫХ ЛИНГВОКУЛЬТУРАХ*.
12. qizi Turaboyeva, S. Z., & qizi Tashpulatova, D. X. (2022). O‘ZBEK VA INGLIZ TILLARIDAGI AXLOQIY QADRIYATLAR MAZMUNINI IFODALOVCHI BIRLIKARNING LINGVOKULTUROLOGIK XUSUSIYATLARI. *Academic research in modern science*, 1(1), 143-147.
13. Ташпулатова, Д. Х. К., & Умурзакова, Б. Э. (2023). НЕРВНАЯ СИСТЕМА. *Academic research in educational sciences*, 4(TMA Conference), 303-309.
14. Tashpulatova, D. K. K., & Jiyenbayeva, B. (2023). THE IMPACT OF LEARNING A LANGUAGE ON THE BRAIN FUNCTION. *Academic research in educational sciences*, 4(TMA Conference), 310-314.
15. NAVOI, A., & BABUR, Z. M. (2022). RESEARCH AND EDUCATION.